

Assessment of the Level of Knowledge on Child Abuse among Parents of Children

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Children are the future of their nation. They should be protected till their full development. The awareness regarding negative effects of child abuse among their parents is very important to prevent any risk to any child. **Material and Methods:** A quasi- experimental research study was conducted to assess the level of knowledge on child abuse among parents of children with age group of 6-12 years and to find association between pre-test and post-test knowledge score on child abuse among parents. Sixty parents of children with the age group of 6-12 years residing in selected urban area at Sri Ganganagar were selected as sample in which each 30 samples were for experimental & control group respectively. The purposive sampling technique was used for data collection. The structured interview questionnaire was used as a tool for both the experimental and control group for pre-test and post-test. **Results:** The mean post- test knowledge score (23.8) of parents was higher than the mean pre-test knowledge score (18.3) of parents in experimental group. The calculated 't' value (23.21*), which is significant at $p < 0.05$ level. **Conclusion:** It indicates that the Information, Education and Communication module on child abuse was effective in improving the knowledge of the parents.

KEYWORDS: Assess; Effectiveness; Information, Education & Communication; Knowledge; Child abuse; Parents; Children

INTRODUCTION

Child abuse is a state of emotional, physical, economic and sexual maltreatment meted out to a person below the age of eighteen and is a globally prevalent phenomenon. However, in India, as in many other countries, there has been no understanding of the extent, magnitude and trends of the problem. Existing socio-economic conditions also render some children vulnerable and more at risk to abuse, exploitation and neglect. It is about time that we recognize this and take remedial measures. The aim of the study was to develop a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon of child abuse among parents, with a view to facilitate the knowledge of parents on child abuse for appropriate care meant to effectively curb and control the problem of child abuse.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A quasi- experimental research study was conducted to assess the level of knowledge on child abuse among parents

RESULTS

PART - I: DATA ON SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES OF PARENTS OF CHILDREN IN THE AGE GROUP OF 6-12 YEARS OF EXPERIMENTAL GROUP.

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of children with age group of 6-12 years and to find association between pre-test and post-test knowledge score on child abuse among parents. Sixty parents of children with the age group of 6-12 years residing in selected urban area at Sri Ganganagar were selected as sample in which each 30 samples were for experimental & control group respectively. The non-probability purposive sampling technique was used for data collection. The self-administered interview questionnaire was used as a tool after taking the written consent from each study participant, for both the experimental and control group for pre-test and post-test. After that Information, Education and Communication on Child Abuse was administered to the experimental group and no interventions to the control group. Thereafter the post -test assessment of level of knowledge was done for both te experimental and control group. The Data for the final analysis were analyzed by using SPSS software program version 17.00.

Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Socio-Demographic Variables of parents of children in the age group of 6-12 years of experimental group.

N=30

S. No.	Demographic Variables	Respondents	
		Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
1	Age of the Father		
	a) 25 - 27 years	14	46.7
	b) 28 - 30 years	14	46.7
	c) > 30 years	2	6.7
2	Age of the Mother		
	a) 25 - 27 years	21	70.0
	b) 28 - 30 years	7	23.3
	c) > 30 years	2	6.7
3	Parity		
	a. First child	17	56.7
	b. Second child	8	26.7
	c. Third child	3	10.0
	d. Any other information	2	6.7
4	Age of child		
	a. 6- 8years	15	50
	b. 9-10 years	9	30
	c. 11-12 years	6	20
5	Sex of child		
	a. Male	12	40
	b. Female	18	60
6	Mother's Education		
	a. Illiterate	5	16.7
	b. Primary education	12	40.0
	c. Secondary education	8	26.7
	d. Senior secondary	5	16.7
	e. Graduate	0	0
7	Father's Education		
	a. Illiterate	0	0
	b. Primary education	2	6.7
	c. Secondary education	13	43.3
	d. Senior secondary	10	33.3
	e. Graduate	5	16.7
8	Mother's occupation		
	a. Housewife	20	66.7
	b. Private employee	10	33.3
	c. Government employee	0	0
	d. Self-employed	0	0
9	Father's occupation		
	a. Labour	4	13.3
	b. Private employee	15	50.0
	c. Government employee	6	20.0
	d. Self-employed	5	16.7
10	Family monthly income		
	a. Rs.5000	2	6.7
	b. Rs. 5001-Rs.10000	7	23.3
	c. Rs.10001 - Rs. 20000	13	43.3
	d. Rs.>20000	8	26.7
11	Religion		
	a. Hindu	18	60.0
	b. Sikh	12	40.0
	c. Muslim	0	0
	d. Christian	0	0
12	Type of family		
	a. Nuclear family	6	20.0
	b. Joint family	24	80.0
	c. Extended family	0	0

13	Number of children in the family		
	a. 1	17	56.7
	b. 2	8	26.7
	c. 3	3	10.0
	d. >3	2	6.7
14	Do you know about child abuse before?		
	a. Yes	30	100
	b. No	0	0
15	If yes, through which form (source of knowledge)		
	a. Television	15	50.0
	b. Radio	3	10.0
	c. Newspaper	5	16.7
	d. Friends	4	13.3
	e. Relatives	3	10.0

PART - II: DATA ON SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES OF PARENTS OF CHILDREN IN THE AGE GROUP OF 6-12 YEARS OF CONTROL GROUP.

Frequency and percentage distribution of Socio-Demographic Variables of parents of children in the age group of 6-12 years of control group.

N=30

S. No.	Demographic Variables	Respondents	
		Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
1	Age of the Father		
	a) 15 yrs	5	16.7
	b) 16yrs	13	43.3
	c) 17 yrs	12	40.0
2	Age of the Mother		
	a) 25 - 27 years	9	30.0
	b) 28 - 30 years	5	16.7
	c) > 30 years	16	53.3
3	Parity		
	a. First child	12	40.0
	b. Second child	7	23.3
	c. Third child	11	36.7
	d. Any other information	0	0
4	Age of child		
	a. 6- 8years	17	56.7
	b. 9-10 years	9	30.0
	c. 11-12 years	4	13.3
5	Sex of child		
	a. Male	13	43.3
	b. Female	17	56.7
6	Mother's Education		
	a. Illiterate	7	23.3
	b. Primary education	10	33.3
	c. Secondary education	2	6.7
	d. Senior secondary	5	16.7
	e. Graduate	6	20.0
7	Father's Education		
	a. Illiterate	3	10.0
	b. Primary education	6	20.0
	c. Secondary education	2	6.7
	d. Senior secondary	8	26.7
	e. Graduate	11	36.7
8	Mother's occupation		
	a. Housewife	15	50.0
	b. Private employee	4	13.3
	c. Government employee	8	26.7
	d. Self-employed	3	10.0

9	Father's occupation		
	a. Labour	3	10.0
	b. Private employee	12	40.0
	c. Government employee	9	30.0
	d. Self-employed	6	20.0
10	Family monthly income		
	a. Rs.5000	5	16.7
	b. Rs. 5001-Rs.10000	0	0
	c. Rs.10001 - Rs. 20000	14	46.7
	d. Rs.>20000	11	36.7
11	Religion		
	a. Hindu	7	23.3
	b. Sikh	9	30.0
	c. Muslim	10	33.3
	d. Christian	4	13.3
12	Type of family		
	a. Nuclear family	9	30.0
	b. Joint family	10	33.3
	c. Extended family	11	36.7
13	Number of children in the family		
	a. 1	14	46.7
	b. 2	6	20.0
	c. 3	10	33.3
	d. >3	0	0
14	Do you know about child abuse before?		
	a. Yes	30	100
	b. No	0	0
15	If yes, through which form (source of knowledge)		
	a. Television	12	40.0
	b. Radio	4	13.3
	c. Newspaper	6	20.0
	d. Friends	4	13.3
	e. Relatives	4	13.3

PART: III ANALYSE THE PRE AND POST-TEST LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE SCORES ON CHILD ABUSE AMONG PARENTS OF CHILDREN IN THE AGE GROUP OF 6-12 YEARS OF EXPERIMENTAL GROUP.

Mean, SD, Range and Mean score percentage, Mean difference of Pre and Post-Test level of knowledge score and 't' Value of experimental group.

N=30

Maximum possible score	Pre-test knowledge score			Mean Score %	Post-test Knowledge Score			Mean Score %	Mean Differences	't' Value
	Mean	SD	Range		Mean	SD	Range			
30	18.3	5.7	6 - 20	61	23.8	3.5	17-30	79.33	5.5	23.21*

PART-IV: ANALYSE THE POST-TEST LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE SCORES ON CHILD ABUSE AMONG PARENTS OF CHILDREN IN THE AGE GROUP OF 6-12 YEARS OF EXPERIMENTAL GROUP AND CONTROL GROUP.

Mean, Mean Score percentage, Mean difference of Post-Test level of knowledge score and 't' Value of experimental and control group.

N=30

Maximum possible score	Experimental group Post-test knowledge score N=30	Mean Score %	Control group Post-test Knowledge Score N=30	Mean Score %	Mean Differences	't' Value
	Mean		Mean			
30	23.8	79.33	12.86	42.86	10.94	9.83*

PART-V: DATA ON ASSOCIATION BETWEEN MEAN LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE SCORE ON CHILD ABUSE AMONG PARENTS OF CHILDREN IN THE AGE GROUP OF 6-12 YEARS OF EXPERIMENTAL GROUP WITH SELECTED SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES.

Frequency, Percentage Distribution and χ^2 Value of Level of Knowledge on child abuse among parents of children in the age group of 6-12 years of experimental group with selected socio-demographic variables.

N=30

S. No.	Demographic Variables	Inadequate		Moderately Adequate		χ^2 Value
		Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)	
1	Mother's education					13.13 df=3 S
	a. Illiterate	5	16.6	0	0	
	b. Primary education	9	30	3	10	
	c. Secondary education	6	20	2	6.6	
2	Father's Education					7.9 df=3 S
	a. Primary education	2	6.6	0	0	
	b. Secondary education	11	36.6	2	6.6	
	c. Senior secondary	6	20	4	13.3	
3	Mother's occupation					0.0 df=1 S
	a. Housewife	14	46.6	6	20	
	b. Private employee	6	20	4	13.3	

S=Significant df = degrees of freedom

DISCUSSION

The study findings revealed that the pre-test level of knowledge among experimental group out of 30 parents, most of them, 20(66.3%) had inadequate level of knowledge, 10(33.3%) had moderately adequate level of knowledge and none of them had adequate level of knowledge. In post-test 22(73.3%) had adequate level of knowledge, 8(26.6%) had moderately adequate level of knowledge and none of them had inadequate level of knowledge. The study findings also revealed that the pre-test level of knowledge among control group out of 30 parents, most of them 19(63.3%) had moderately level of knowledge, 10(33.3%) had inadequate level of knowledge and 1(3.3%) had adequate level of knowledge. In post-test 11(37%) had inadequate level of knowledge, 17(57%) had moderately adequate level of knowledge and 2(6%) had adequate level of knowledge.

The level of knowledge on child abuse among parents of children in the age group of 6-12 years of experimental group results revealed that the pre-test overall mean score was 18.3 with the SD of 5.7 and the range was 6-20, with the mean score percentage of 61 and in post-test the overall mean score was increased to 23.8 with the SD of 3.5 and the range was 17-30, with the mean score percentage 79.33. The mean difference of pre and post-test was 5.5. The calculated 't' value was 23.21* which is significant at $p < 0.05$ level. This indicates that the Information, Education and Communication module on child abuse was effective in improving the knowledge of parents.

There was a significant association found between the level of knowledge on Child Abuse among parents of children in the age group of 6-12 years of experimental group with selected socio-demographic variables such as education of mother, education of father and mother's occupation.

CONCLUSION

The main conclusions drawn from this present study was to assess the effectiveness of Information Education and Communication Module on Child Abuse among parents of children in the age group of 6-12 years, there was significant increase in the level of knowledge among parents in

experimental group but not in control group. And also calculated 't' value shown that the Information, education and Communication module on child abuse was very much effective in improving the knowledge of parents.

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